

THE MAIN PROBLEMS OF INCREASING THE PROFITABILITY OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES AND CREATING AN INVESTMENT SPACE IN NAMANGAN REGION

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Abstract: This article provides information about the main problems and their solutions to increase the profitability of industrial enterprises and create an investment space in the Namangan region.

Key words: profitability, investment, foreign economic activity, economic policy, joint venture, socialist principle.

Liberalization of foreign economic activity, improvement of legal, socio-economic and other conditions that ensure the attraction of foreign investments to the national economy, consistent implementation of the policy of open doors to foreign investments, the priority way of ensuring the economic independence of the country. Incorporation in the directions is one of the main principles of the economic policy conducted in our republic. From this point of view, the regions should have their own contributions in the implementation of macroeconomic stabilization, development and strengthening of the national economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

At the same time when the leadership of the republic is introducing a favorable investment environment for economic entities working in cooperation with foreign investors in Uzbekistan for the development of their activities, various loans and tax incentives are being introduced to attract investments, the activities of joint enterprises in Namangan region are at the same time. it's so slow. Therefore, it is appropriate for justice, statistics, tax authorities, and banking institutions to determine the most effective measures within the framework of the law in relation to joint ventures that are operating or not operating in violation of relevant laws and other regulatory documents.

In the conditions of the current market economy and the independence (freedom) of the socio-economic development of the regions, each region should try to strengthen its economy based on its internal capabilities. The reason is that the former socialist principles, that is, management and planning in one center, the placement and development of all industrial enterprises by the state in one or another region, have lost their power. It is in such conditions that it is extremely urgent to deepen market reforms with the help of developing small and medium-sized businesses in the region, creating a favorable investment space, and attracting foreign investments here.

During the period of transition to new economic relations and reconstruction of society on a democratic basis, priority attention is paid to the correct and effective placement of production forces in the regions. Of course, in such a situation, each region tries to form a separate economic space, changes in the forms of social organization of production take place in them. First of all, medium-sized and especially small industrial enterprises will increase in the integration of production, and in the specialization, the production of finished products

will be given great importance. At the same time, the process of combining will increase. Because, on the one hand, due to the lack of raw materials in large enterprises, they create additional and complementary shops or departments, and on the other hand, small and medium-sized enterprises also start production of various products.[2]

The economy of Namangan region is distinguished by its ease in the economic environment of the republic. However, due to the dense population and the fact that 62.0 percent of the population lives in rural areas, as well as the lack of development of infrastructure networks, it creates unique problems in creating an investment space in the region. [3]

Naturally, it is implemented through the development of a modern infrastructure system in rural areas, the introduction of industry into the countryside, and the expansion of service networks. After all, financial resources are needed for this. A foreign investor will not invest in a rural area where there are no conditions for profit. At this point, it should be noted that solving existing territorial problems is important for a country or a region, while a foreign investor mainly wants a favorable environment that provides faster and more profit.

In order to attract foreign investments to rural areas, first of all, it is required to improve the infrastructure system and use the available opportunities, to solve problems. In fact, it is impossible to establish enterprises with participation of foreign investments without creating the necessary conditions aimed at improving the infrastructure, that is, production and the living conditions of the population. The fact that these problems have not been well resolved in the region, and that the places are not ready or provided in terms of infrastructure, creates a number of problems in creating an investment space here.

Also, the analysis of the strategic goals of placing foreign investments in the region is not deep. Contracts and joint ventures are being formed hastily without thorough study of the economic possibilities of the regions and without economic analysis. This complicates the establishment of their activities. In particular, the lack of experience in the preparation of investment projects and the preparation of technical and economic indicators at a low level do not give positive results.

In general, the current state of the social infrastructure system almost corresponds to the indicators of the Republic of Uzbekistan. However, in the near future, the provision of natural gas and roads, regular supply of clean drinking water for the stable formation of investment space in the region is one of the urgent problems of today.

One of the main indicators of the socio-economic development of regions and countries is the level of employment of the population and labor resources. In addition, this is the most urgent problem of the transition period, and stabilization of the country's micro-economy and regional policy should be primarily aimed at preventing unemployment in the regions and improving the social environment. [1] Studies show that the existence of political stability in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the hard work of the population, the fact that the country has great economic potential, the abundance of various rare and valuable minerals and other factors attract many foreign investments to the national and regional economy. allows to do. To a certain extent, such opportunities exist in Namangan region.

Conclusion:

Increasing the profitability of industrial enterprises in the Namangan region is closely related to the profound quality changes that are taking place in today's economy and social life. Such features are, firstly, the change of the demographic situation in the area, i.e. natural

reproduction and migration movements, secondly, the transport geographical location of the region, thirdly, meeting the needs of society and eliminating socio-ecological problems, fourthly, scientific the state of using technical achievements, fifthly, the indicators of participation in the domestic and foreign markets, sixthly, the steady development of the process of intensification of the entire national economic complex. These features require the implementation of regional forecasting aimed at the complex development of increasing the profitability of industrial enterprises in the region.

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